

ADAPTIVE FUZZY LOGIC CONTROLLER PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEM USING Z-SOURCE MULTILEVEL INVERTER

R.Goutham Govind Raju¹, A Kathiravan², S Suguna³, S Sivakumar⁴
^{1,2,3,4} Assistant Professor, Department of Electrical and Electronics Engg,
^{1,2,3,4} Rajiv Gandhi College of Engg and Tech

Abstract. This paper presents a Multilevel Inverter based on Adaptive fuzzy logic controlled Photovoltaic system with Symmetrical Phase Shift Modulation (PSM) technique which is used with the active device present in the Multilevel Inverter to reduce a power loss and shoot-through problem. The proposed system consists of PV system, Z-source, Multilevel Inverter and a AFLC controller. The Z-source is used to protect the Multilevel Inverter from the shoot-through problem and to reduce the switching loss and switching stress of the device. A switched-capacitor based cascaded multilevel inverter with Symmetrical Phase Shift Modulation technique is used with the controller to evaluate the performance of the proposed system and the output of controllers is compared. The simulation study of the proposed converter is carried out using MATLAB/Simulink with proposed nine level inverter.

Keywords: PSM, AFLC, THD, MLI

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, it is hard to connect a single power semiconductor switch directly to medium- voltage grids (2.3, 3.3, 4.16, or 6.9 kV). For these reasons, a new family of multilevel inverters has emerged as the solution for working with higher voltage levels. The multilevel inverter have been widely studied for various industrial applications such as large motor drives with non-regenerative front ends, merge motor drives with regenerative front ends, applications in power systems [1-5].

The Cascaded Multilevel Inverters structures are probably the most popular topologies. There are many modulation methods to regulate the multilevel inverter; the popular modulations are the space vector modulation, the multicarrier PWM, and the selective harmonic elimination, sub harmonic pulse width modulation, etc [6-10]. A symmetrical phase-shift modulation is introduced into the proposed multilevel inverter. The symmetrical PSM ensures the output voltage of full bridge is symmetrical to the carrier, so voltage levels can be superimposed symmetrically and carrier frequency is twice as that of the out- put frequency.

Initially GA based selective harmonic minimization of a 11 level cascaded inverter using PV panels has been approached for real time computation of switching angles using GA, then High performance PV power generation using z source inverter is used which has Z-source inverter which is an advancement of traditional converter, with a built-in X shaped impedance network. Which is followed by Control and Modulation Scheme for a Cascaded H-Bridge Multi-Level Converter in large scale Photovoltaic System [11-14].

The paper is organized as follows. The system configurations and its simple operation are discussed in Section III. The overall circuit diagram for the system and the simulation results were given in Section IV followed by Section V, which concludes the paper.

II. CIRCUIT DESCRIPTIONS AND OPERATION

The proposed AFLC controller based Z-source MLI for PV application is shown in Fig 1, in which the circuit is divided into four segments namely PV section, z-source section, Inverter section and load. The output form the proposed system is taken by changing the load form resistive to RL load and the obtained result are validates.

Fig 1: Block diagram of AFLC controller based Z-source MLI for PV application

III. PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEM SECTION

A. Solar Cell

A general block diagram of the PVA model for Simulink is given in Fig 2. The block called PVA model is the last stage of the model. This block contains the sub models that are connected to build the final model. A diode (D1) is connected in series with the load circuit to prevent the reverse current flow and the mathematical model of a single PV cell is represented with the block called eqn. 1, 2, 3, 4.

$$V_{pv} = V_c * C_{TV} * C_{TI} * N_s \tag{1}$$

$$V_c = \frac{AKT_c}{e} \left(\frac{I_{pv} + I_0 + I_c}{I_0} \right) - R_s I_c \tag{2}$$

$$I_c = I_{pv} / N_p, I_{pv} = C_{TI} * C_{SI} * I_{SC} \tag{3}$$

$$C_{TV} = 1 + \beta_T (T_c - T_x), C_{SV} = 1 + \beta_T \alpha_s (S_x - S_c) \tag{4}$$

Fig 2: The diagram shows the PV cell model

B. The Boost Converter

A boost converter is a power converter with an output DC voltage greater than its input DC voltage. It is a class of switching mode power supply containing at least two semi-conductors switches and at least one energy storage element. Analysis of the boost converter begins by making these assumptions:

- i. The circuit is operating in the steady state and the inductor current is continuous
- ii. The capacitor is very large, and the output voltage is held constant at voltage V_o .
- iii. The switching period is T , the switch is closed for time DT and open for time $(1-D)T$
- iv. The components are ideal

C. Fuzzy Logic Controller

The Fig.3 (a), (b) and (c), the input variables of the fuzzy controller (E, CE) are derived from the actual signals (e, ce) by multiplying with the corresponding scale gains (SE, SCE), and then converted to the linguistic variables given in tabular column 1 shows the fuzzy rules for the system

Fig 3 (a) Membership functions for Input E

Fig 3(b): Membership functions for Input CE

Fig 3(c): Membership functions for Output (delta D).

Table1: Fuzzy Membership Rules

E	CE				
	NB	NS	ZO	PS	PB
NB	ZO	ZO	NB	NB	NB
NS	ZO	ZO	NS	NS	NS
ZO	NS	ZO	ZO	ZO	PS
PS	PS	PS	PS	ZO	ZO
PB	PB	PB	PB	ZO	ZO

Here, the adaptive mechanism contains three parts as follows and given in tabular column 2,

(A) First, in order to eliminate the high-frequency noise, we adopt the moving average filter to compute PPV as:

$$P_{pv}(n) = \frac{[P_{pv}(n-1) + P_{pv}(n-2)]}{2} \quad (5)$$

Similarly, the sunlight intensity affects the current IPV of PV module, so we adopt this method to estimate the trend of IPV as:

$$I_{pv}(n) = \frac{[I_{pv}(n-1) + I_{pv}(n-2)]}{2} \quad (6)$$

(B) Based on PPV(n) and IPV(n), plus comparing with previous PPV(n-1) and IPV(n-1), we can compute their differences. Then, it is obvious that the differences of PPV and IPV are either possible or negative, respectively. Thus, it can be summarized as 4 trends, and going a step further, 4 rules for adaptive mechanism can be suggested as shown in Table 3. 2, these rules are,

(i) **Rule 1 and Rule 2:** A fixed parameter is inadequate in applications when the operating conditions have change, and it is not reliable. Thus, the duty cycle can be modified by rule 1 and rule 2, and then the adaptive value ΔK is assigned to $K1=-0.25$. Because ΔK is a smaller negative value now, the duty cycle will be modified to decrease a little.

(ii) **Rule 3 and Rule 4:** Similarly, the duty cycle can be modified by rule 3 and rule 4, and then the adaptive value ΔK is assigned to $K2=-0.3$. Because ΔK is a bigger negative value now, the duty cycle will be modified to decrease a lot. (C) To combine this adaptive value ΔK and V_c from defuzzication, the duty-cycle control voltage ΔV_c can be obtained as:

$$\Delta V_c = V_c + \Delta K(7)$$

By using the ΔV_c , the duty cycle D is determined via the PWM block for the control of MOSFET SB so as to realize the MPP search.

Table 2: Adaptive Mechanism for Fuzzy Logic

Rule	$[P_{pv}(n) - P_{pv}(n-1)] > 0$	$[I_{pv}(n) - I_{pv}(n-1)] > 0$	Duty cycle	Select of ΔK
1	truth	truth	Decrease a little	K1
2	false	false		
3	truth	false	Decrease a lot	K2
4	false	truth		

IV.Z-SOURCE INVERTER

The basic Z-source converter structure proposed as shown in fig 4 given below with equivalent circuit. It employs a unique impedance network to couple the converter main circuit to the power source, load, for providing unique features that cannot be observed in the traditional V and I source converters where a capacitor and inductor are used, respectively. It consist of a two port network that consists of a split-inductor and capacitors and connected in X shape is employed to provide an impedance source coupling the converter to the dc source, load, or another converter.

Fig 4: Equivalent circuit of Z source inverter

V. MULTI LEVEL INVERTER

The proposed circuit is shown in Fig 5 which is made up of the SC frontend and cascaded H-Bridge backend with RL load. If the numbers of voltage levels obtained by SC frontend and cascaded H-Bridge backend are N_1 and N_2 , respectively, the number of voltage levels is $2 \times N_1 \times N_2 + 1$ in the entire operation cycle. A. Circuit Topology the circuit shows the topology of nine-level inverter ($N_1=2, N_2=2$), where S_1, S_2, S_1, S_2 as the switching devices of SC circuits (SC1 and SC2) are used to convert the series or parallel connection of C_1 and C_2 . $S_{1a}, S_{1b}, S_{1c}, S_{1d}, S_{2a}, S_{2b}, S_{2c}, S_{2d}$ are the switching devices of cascaded H-Bridge. To verify the feasibility of the proposed scheme, a Simulink model is developed in MATLAB, the simulation results is shown and discussed.

A. Simulation Results for Cascaded MLI with R load.

The output load voltage waveform of cascaded multilevel inverter with R load. This output can be characteristics between voltage v_s time. The output voltage value is 375V in Fig 6 with output load current is shown in Fig 7 is 37.5A and by using FFT window display the THD value is 20.32%

Fig 5:Proposed Circuit topology of cascaded nine-level inverter

Fig 6:Output voltage waveform cascaded multilevel inverter with R load.

Fig 7: Output current waveform of cascaded multilevel inverter with R load

Figure 8: THD value of output load voltage

There are two PV system is used as a input to the Z-source cascaded MLI with R load and PI controller. Input voltage of the PV1 and PV2 are shown in Fig 9 & 10 resp, PV1 output voltage value is 140V and PV2 outputvoltagevalueis98V, which is common to all the circuit.

Fig 9: Output voltage waveform of solar1

Fig 10: Output voltage waveform of solar2

B. Simulation Circuit of Z-Source Cascaded MLI with R Load and AFLC Controller

The Output load voltage waveform is shown in Fig 11. This voltage is taken across the R is 430V. The output load current waveform is shown in Fig 12 is 42A. The THD value of output load voltage is shown in Fig 13. The THD value is calculated for output load voltage by using FFT window display calculated for 3 number of is 14.03%.

Fig 11: Output voltage waveform of Z-source Cascaded MLI withR load and AFL controller

Fig 12: Output voltage waveform of Z-source cascaded MLI withR load and PI controller

Fig 13: THD value of output load voltage

C. Simulation Circuit of a Cascaded Multi level Inverter with RL Load

The Output load voltage is 380V. Output load current waveform is shown in Fig 14. This current is taken across the load is 38A which is shown in Fig 15. THD value of output load voltage is shown in Fig 16. The THD value is calculated for output load voltage by using FFT window display calculated for 5 number of cycle is 20.60%.

Fig 14: Output voltage waveform of cascaded multilevel inverter with RL load

Fig 15: Output current waveform of cascaded multilevel inverter with RL load

Fig 16: THD value of output load voltage

C. Simulation Result of Z-Source Cascaded MLI with RL Load and AFLC Controller

The output load voltage waveform of z-source cascaded MLI with RL load and AFLC controller is shown in Fig 17. With 450V. The output load current is shown in Fig 18, which is 42 Amps THD value of output load voltage of Z-source cascaded MLI with RL load and PI controller is shown in Fig 19. The THD value is calculated for output load voltage by using FFT window display calculated for 5 number of cycle and THD value is 14.28%. The simulation outputs are compared in the table 4.1 with both R load and RL load output

Fig 17: Output voltage waveform of Z-source cascaded MLI with RL load and AFLC controller

Fig 18: Output current waveform of Z-source cascaded MLI with RL load and AFLC controller

Fig 19: THD value of output load voltage

Table 4.1: Comparison of Simulation Results of various systems

Methods	PV ₁ =140V, PV ₂ =98V		
	V _{output}	I _{output}	% THD
Conventional with R load	375V	35.5A	20.32%
Z Source based R load with AFLC	430V	42A	14.03%
Conventional with RL load	380V	38A	20.6%
Z Source based RL load with AFLC	450V	42A	14.28%

VI. Conclusion

In this paper, the simulation of a Multilevel Inverter based on Adaptive fuzzy logic controlled Photovoltaic simulation model is executed. The Z-source is used to prevent the MLI from the shoot-through problem and to reduce the switching loss and switching stress of the device. The switch in the multilevel inverter is turn on and turns off by Symmetrical Phase Shift Modulation (PSM) technique, multilevel inverter is constructed by a switched-capacitor frontend and H-Bridge backend. The increasing number of voltage levels can significantly reduce the output harmonics. AFLC controller is evaluating the performance of the proposed system. The output voltage THD value of both controllers with Rand RL is compared. From the simulation, results AFLC controller gives reduced THD value compare to conventional method.

VII. REFERENCES

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VIII. APPENDIX**Table 6.1:** Simulated Parameter and Output Values of Cascaded Multilevel Inverter

PARAMETER	VALUE
Input voltage source(V_{dc1})	100V
Input current(I_{in1})	40A
Input voltage source(V_{dc2})	100V
Input current(I_{in2})	45A
Source capacitor(C_1)	330 μ F
Source capacitor(C_2)	330 μ F
Resistive load(R)	10 Ω
Output load voltage(V_{out})	375V
Output load current(I_{out})	37.5A

Table 6.2: Simulated Parameter and Output Values Z-Source Cascaded MLI with R Load and AFL Controller

PARAMETER	VALUE	
PV1 output voltage (V_{dc1})	62V	
Solar output current(I_{in1})	59A	
PV2 output voltage(V_{dc2})	61V	
Solar output current(I_{in2})	60A	
Z-source Parameter	L1	1mH
	L2	1mH
	C1	330 μ F
	C2	330 μ F
Source capacitor(C_1)	330 μ F	
Source capacitor(C_2)	330 μ F	
Resistive load(R)	10 Ω	
Output load voltage(V_{out})	430V	
Output load current(I_{out})	41A	